

PEDAGOGICAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL DEVELOPMENT AND SOCIAL RELATIONSHIPS OF PRE-SCHOOL CHILDREN

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Annotation: this article examines issues such as the social psychological development of preschool children as well as their access to social relationships. Social and personal development is the development of a positive attitude of the child to himself, to other people, to the surrounding world and to the communicative and social competence of the child. At the moment, the most important basis for the full-fledged social and personal development of the child is his positive self-awareness: his abilities, confidence, he is very well loved.

Key words: aesthetic, intellectual, preschool age, individual, communication skills, constructive material.

Creating conditions for comprehensive development of preschool children intellectually, morally, aesthetically and physically requires. Improvement of the educational process should be carried out on the basis of assessment of the level of development of children and their readiness for general primary education, as well as their social, personal, emotional, speech, physical and creative development.

All parents realized that their growing children were successful in communicating with their peers. After all, through communication with children, character and behavior are formed in society and in individuals. Therefore, social adaptation is very important for preschool children. To go to any collective, people need time to learn and "discover" themselves, and children learn to live in a community, which directly affects their development.

Social development of children of preschool age includes the child's learning of society's values, traditions and culture, as well as social characteristics of a person that help him live a comfortable life in society. In the process of social adaptation, children learn to live by certain rules and take into account the norms of behavior.

In the process of communication, the child has a social environment, which is provided by his immediate environment: parents, kindergarten teachers and peers. Social potential is realized due to the child's active communication and information exchange. Children who are socially irresponsible often reject the experiences of others and do not communicate with adults and peers. This can lead to antisocial behavior in the future due to the lack of acquisition of cultural skills and the loss of necessary social qualities.

Social and personal development is the development of a child's positive attitude towards himself, other people, the world around him, and children's communicative and social competence. Currently, the most important basis for a child's full social and personal development is his positive self-concept: confidence in his abilities, he is good, he is loved.

In the senior preschool age, great attention is paid to the formation of a unique holistic idea: the teacher encourages children to listen to their feelings, to talk about their feelings and experiences. The organized joint activity of the teacher and children is aimed at finding the child for his place in the society of his peers, emphasizing his Self, putting himself against others, taking an active position in various social relations, where I I act equally with others. This ensures the child's development of a new level of self-awareness, solves the problems of socio-moral development and upbringing of preschool children.

The child learns to understand that his acceptance by others depends on the acceptance of others. Self-knowledge, an adequate attitude towards oneself

creates the need for an appreciative attitude towards the people around. In preschool age, the role of emotional experiences that a child receives as a result of living in a moral situation and making moral choices is very important. The teacher creates conditions for the formation of the experience of moral activity in an older preschool child. The main qualities that determine the successful social and personal development of a preschool child:

- Positive attitude of the child towards himself (self-esteem, self-awareness, self-confidence formation);
- Positive attitude towards other people (adequate interpersonal relationships with adults and peers built on the basis of cooperation, mutual responsibility);
- Value directions; communication skills (adequate communication with adults and peers);
- Social skills (adequate behavior in different situations).

In addition, in the process of self-evaluation of a person, his evaluation is connected with the public and with the evaluation of members of the public, whose opinion is important for a person for certain reasons. As for the child's concept, at preschool age it is still poorly structured and very flexible.

From the age of 4, the child has the first thoughts about what can happen. The child's cognitive activity becomes unusually active and constant, its main driving force is interest. The child can already move freely and is fluent enough to ask questions and understand the answers received. Parents must not suppress the cognitive activity of the child.

A child's use of the pronoun "I" is an indicator of his growing sense of identity. The meaning of a unique name in the concept of a child. Even before the child begins to speak, he already knows his name and reacts to it. This name is then included in the "Image" and used as a means of self-realization.

The most important task of the child's individual experience is to provide the

cognitive part of his self-image with real knowledge about himself, his abilities and possibilities. The evaluative influence of adults on the child has both emotional and cognitive elements, so they direct his attention not only to the good and bad aspects of their behavior, but also serve as models for forming ideas about themselves. From this point of view, the nature of the influence of adults' assessment is of decisive importance in the process of forming the ideas of the preschool child about his own abilities.

Juvenile evaluation has the most negative impact on how children perceive the results of their actions. This causes children to mistrust, conflicts, disagreements and even refusal to work.

Overestimation of adults has a double effect on the behavior of a preschool child: it can distort the child's ideas in the direction of exaggerating the results of his actions; or on the contrary, it mobilizes his strength, stimulates the child's optimism and confidence in achieving good results.

Information about his abilities collected in individual experience in a preschool child, when confirmed in the experience of communicating with others, becomes constructive material for the formation of an Image. Therefore, the role of the clear evaluative influence of adults in the formation of the child's objective ideas about himself is so great. The experience of communicating with adults is the main source of evaluative influence for a child, under the influence of which he forms an attitude to the real world, to himself and to other people. The dependence of the preschool child's behavior on the influence of adults is inversely proportional to the age of the child: the younger the child, the less critical he perceives the opinions of adults, and his ideas about his abilities are based only on the concrete results of the activity. In older preschool years, adults retain the same authority over the child as they do over the toddler, but their assessment of the preschool child is based on the prism of these results and conclusions, prompting the child in his personal experience. In the process of

forming the child's ideas about his abilities, the experience of contact with peers is primarily a context for comparison with "beings like himself" and serves as a basis for acquiring the basic skills of collective life. In addition, communication with peers is a means of exchange of evaluative opinions at the same time, as a result of which the child has the opportunity to see himself through the eyes of his peers.

Conclusion: In conclusion, it can be said that the formation of clear ideas of the child about himself implies a harmonious combination of his personal experience and the knowledge and knowledge about himself that the child collects through communication with other people. If this harmony is disturbed due to the lack of individual experience or favorable conditions for the child's communication with others, then his ideas about himself will gradually begin to deteriorate depending on higher or lower levels. Attitude towards others, communication and social skills are formed in the process of interaction with people around the child. Thus, the number of situations in a child's individual activity is about twice as large as his relationship with someone, 2-3-year-old children mainly communicate with adults. This communication of the child takes the form of turning to the adult when there is any difficulty or with the purpose of the game (for example, they grab a toy and then hide it behind their back). In three-year-old children, these appeals are also related to the requirement to evaluate the results of their activities.

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